

THE ROLE OF TEACHERS IN CHILDREN'S LIVES AND METHODS OF PROPER EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article explores the role of teachers in children's lives, focusing on the attention, care, education, and knowledge they provide. It also offers various insights into how students can be taught properly, with examples of different methods used in teaching.

Keywords: student and teacher, education, pedagogical research methods, pedagogical experiment, method.

In our country, great attention is being paid to the education system at the level of state policy. Thanks to the benefits of independence, significant changes have occurred in the field of preschool education, as in all other areas. The strength of any country is determined by its intellectual potential. There are various ways to achieve this potential. The upbringing of a well-rounded person has always been a fundamental requirement and primary goal of social society throughout history. Naturally, in the current context of educational reforms, the upbringing of a well-rounded individual continues to hold great importance. The socio-economic and cultural-spiritual changes occurring at the present stage of societal development require radical reforms in education, freeing it from ideological views and remnants of the past. This involves preparing highly qualified, modern personnel who meet the high moral and ethical standards of developed democratic states and improving the efficiency of the educational process.

The role of a teacher in students' lives, and indeed in the lives of all humanity, is incomparable. Teachers teach students many things as they grow and mature. They support them in various ways and are invaluable individuals in this world. Even great scholars have reached their level thanks to the help of their teachers. As the great Alexander the Great once said: "My father brought me into this world, but my teacher helped me reach this level. My father brought me from the sky to the earth, while my teacher raised me from the earth to the sky." These words carry deep meaning. We, too, must always respect our teachers, as their role in our lives is irreplaceable.

One of the main methods of properly teaching students is communication between the teacher and the student. A teacher's ability to communicate with their students requires a certain level of skill. They must know how to communicate and continuously improve their communication skills. A teacher must also know how to conduct a class effectively, utilize various teaching methods such as discussions, lectures, and storytelling, and establish communication with students throughout the educational process.

For a teacher to establish communication with a student, they must possess sufficient skills and continually ask themselves the following questions and strive to answer them:

What to teach?

Whom to teach?

How to teach?

What to teach: a) Understanding innovations in science, comprehending new scientific terminology, and fully mastering the subject matter; b) Developing skills, competencies, and abilities; c) Establishing connections between different subjects; d) Understanding the content of education within a clear system.

Whom to teach: a) Identifying certain psychological characteristics of students (memory, speech, thinking) and determining their level of education and upbringing; b) Predicting potential difficulties as students move from one level to another; c) Considering students' motivations and opinions when organizing the educational process. g) Organizing their pedagogical work by taking into account various psychological changes and developments in students; d) Working with gifted students and organizing individual work.

How to teach: a) Utilizing a combination of different teaching and educational methods, considering the effort and time required during the process.

The main methods of pedagogical influence include demand, expectations, encouragement, punishment, and public opinion.

Demand is a widely used method in practice, which manifests the teacher's personal attitude toward the student during the educational process, either encouraging or halting certain behaviors.

Demand is the initial method of pedagogical influence and plays a crucial role in developing a student's sense of responsibility and accountability towards themselves.

Encouragement and punishment are used to correct students' behavior, meaning they provide additional reinforcement for positive behavior and help stop inappropriate actions. Public opinion ensures that students' socially beneficial

activities are regularly and comprehensively encouraged. Means of influence through mutual exchange of opinions include persuasion, influence, and mutual exchange of ideas. Persuasion as a method of pedagogical influence is applied in the form of educational information, creative discussions, debates, and political information during lessons. Influence affects a person's psyche without conscious control and is reflected in their actions, motives, and aspirations. Influence involves a psychological impact that is perceived by the individual without sufficient awareness or control.

In conclusion, if a teacher has experience and a deep love for their profession, they will undoubtedly raise successful students. For this to happen, the teacher must thoroughly learn excellent teaching methods and be prepared psychologically for any situations.

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